

Creating the
future of Lithuania

2014-2020 Operational
Programme for the
European Union Funds
Investments in Lithuania

MEMORY PRACTICES IN THE MATRIX

Costis Dallas, Rimvydas Laužikas

Connective Research Group, Faculty of Communication, Vilnius University

This presentation reports on research conducted as part of “Connective digital memory in borderlands: a mixed-methods study of cultural identity, heritage communication and digital curation on social networks”. The Connective project is funded by the European Social Fund under grant agreement 09.3.3-LMT-K-712-17-0027 with the Research Council of Lithuania (LMTLT).

TOPIC

Investigating the use
of **ChatGPT** to **analyze**
and **produce** speculative
SNS conversations
on Lithuanian
contested heritage

THE CONNECTIVE PROJECT

Corpus of over 30,000 Facebook conversations

4 languages

9 themes

Over 100 topics, identified by query terms - 'bags of words'

Representing researcher-selected aspects of contested, excluded and traumatic heritage

Corpus supported by Neo4j graph database and MaxQDA qualitative content analysis tool

HERITAGE, MEMORY AND IDENTITY ON LITHUANIAN SOCIAL MEDIA

SNS conversation on the removal by Vilnius city council of a public monument to **Petras Cvirka**, a controversial Soviet poet and actor
Photo, link to **delfi.t news story**, 320 **comments**

Emoticons: 167 “like”, 92 “angry”, 88 “sad”, 31 “wow”, 29 “love”, 4 “haha”, 1 “care”

Representation and analysis based on **cultural-semiotic nexus theory**: a synthesis between Yuri Lotman’s **semiosphere theory** and Alfred Gell’s **theory of the art nexus**

CVIRKA CONVERSATION: QUALITATIVE CONTENT ANALYSIS

Proponents of removal

- “bloody collaborator”
- “traitor”
- “a complete minion of the Soviet government”
- “obviously acted against the Lithuanian nation by betraying writers who worked underground”
- recognised by the Soviet establishment
- part of a delegation which brought to Vilnius “Stalin’s sun”

Opponents of removal

- the “history of Lithuania is being destroyed”
- the statue “does not bother anyone”
- it belongs to “our history, good or bad”
- “what a pity [that] we try to erase our past”
- politics should stay out of memorialisation, and Cvirka should be assessed only as poet
- “[t]he destroyers of Lithuanian history will erect some iron four-legged cone [and] will call it art to make our children and grandchildren degenerates”
- will be replaced by “another Vilnius pipe” or “loads of scrap metal [like] on the Green Bridge”

Laužikas, R., & Dallas, C. (forthcoming). The message is the agent: Nexus and semiosphere in social media communication. In E. Zantides & S. Andreou (Eds.), *Semiotics and Visual Communication IV: Myths of Today*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

CVIRKA CONVERSATION: DISCOURSE AND PRAGMATICS

- **Existential presuppositions**
 - who else in public life may have been **complicit to Soviet crimes**
 - how many Lithuanians **supported the Soviet annexation**
- **Stance-taking**
 - to what extent **should negative or dark memories be preserved** or forgotten
- **Identity statements**
 - **"I am one who will never support crimes against humanity and an individual - neither Bolshevik reds nor fascists"**
- **Characterisations and slurs**
 - **"Are you a fan of Stalin's sun bearers?"**
 - **"Use arguments and not Soviet emotion, you flabby belly vatnik"**
 - **"In your account [you are] looking at women's clothes"**

"When one user tells another "you don't want to know the real story, apparently you like it distorted, fanciful", the second user blocks her, adding "you're mad [because] you can't see my posts and personal pictures".

*Conversations are ripe with **presupposition** and **allusion**, while irony or **sarcasm** is often used, as when a user suggests: "We should build sculptures of gravels, birds and pets [rather than of notable people]. This will suit all governments and all eras".*

***Hyperbole** is also at play, for example when another user asks: "When will they start burning the books?".*

SOCIAL MEDIA AS CULTURAL-SEMIOTIC NEXUS

Semiotic translation Abduction of agency

Communicative nexus entities

1. **Indexes:** semiotic expressions on social media which motivate abductive inferences, cognitive interpretations, etc.

2. **Authors:** to whom are ascribed, by abduction, causal responsibility for the existence and characteristics of the index

3. **Recipients:** those in relation to whom, by abduction, indexes are considered to exert agency, or who exert agency via the index

4. **Prototypes:** entities held, by abduction, to be represented in the index, often by virtue of visual resemblance, but not necessarily

Which insights can be derived from **a ChatGPT analysis** of the Facebook conversation on the removal of Petras Cvirka's monument?

Which insights can be derived from speculative Facebook **conversations and comments composed by ChatGPT** on the same issue?

What are the implications of these insights for **populism in social media** communication?

Research questions

Using ChatGPT to analyze an actual Facebook conversation on the removal of Cvirka's statue

A. ANALYSIS

PROMPT: ANALYSIS

For which **identity groups** might the delfi.lt news story about Cvirka's monument be relevant?

- For **historians and cultural heritage specialists**: This group may be interested in the event as an example of **historical memory and cultural heritage management**
- For **Lithuanian patriots and nationalists**: The text may resonate with individuals deeply concerned about **national identity and history**, especially considering the period of **Soviet occupation**
- For **critics of the Soviet past**: Individuals actively **opposing any glorification of Soviet occupation** may view the removal of the monument as a positive step
- For the **community of writers and artists**: Those who value **freedom in literature and the arts** may be interested in the discussion about how to assess the work of artists considering their **political behaviour**

INSIGHTS

Groups proposed **lack a singular criterion of categorization**

Group scope, differentiation, and properties offered is not always justified

Groups may be **overlapping, and internal cohesion may be questioned**

Multiple group membership may be suitably implied

Cf. genAI justifiability problem

COMPARISON: SEMIOTIC COLLECTIVES

ChatGPT-generated

PROPONENTS OF THE REMOVAL

- **Lithuanian patriots and nationalists:** Concerned about **national identity and history**, especially considering the period of **Soviet occupation**
- **Critics of the Soviet past:** Actively **opposing any glorification of Soviet occupation**

OPPONENTS OF THE REMOVAL

- **Historians and cultural heritage specialists:** Viewing the removal in context of **historical memory and cultural heritage management**
- **Community of writers and artists:** Valuing **freedom in literature and the arts**

From analysis of actual thread

PROPONENTS OF THE REMOVAL

Anti-Soviet transitional justice advocates arguing against commemorating the Soviet era, viewed as a period of totalitarian oppression and occupation, and in favour of condemnation of those who collaborated and benefited from the Soviet regime

OPPONENTS OF THE REMOVAL

Heritage and history preservationists, not necessarily or all historians or cultural heritage professionals, advocating that the past should be preserved and not erased

Freedom of artistic expression believers, and advocates of liberal, often pro-European, political values

Soviet supporters and traditionalists in ethical and social issues, incl. those denigrating the moral decline of contemporary society and the West

Contemporary art opponents, expressing anti-elitist sentiment, a banal view of art, and preference for didactic artistic expression

Source: Laužikas & Dallas (forthcoming)

PROMPT: ANALYSIS

How can you **describe the author** of the following comment:

Earlier, everything was destroyed by the Russians, and now by ourselves. Well, what kind of pipe will we build, we are too poor to understand true art.

Original text:

Anksčiau viską griovė rusai, o dabar patys. Na kokį vamzdį pastatys, mes per prasti, kad tikrą meną suprasti.

- **Valuing historical continuity:** Emphasizing the similarities between past and present actions, the author seems to **appreciate historical continuity** and may **feel anguish over the ongoing loss of culture and history**.
- **Critical of current trends:** Drawing comparisons with earlier times and expressing **disappointment in contemporary changes** reflects a critical view of the modern development of society.
- **Skeptical of contemporary art:** The comment "we are too poor to understand true art" conveys a belief that **contemporary artistic expression is either inaccessible or incomprehensible** to the general public.
- **Advocate for traditional values:** Longing for "true art" may indicate a **preference for traditional forms** of artistic expression and **dissatisfaction with contemporary artworks**, which the author may perceive as less valuable or understandable.
- **Patriotically inclined:** The phrase "previously everything was destroyed by the Russians, and now by ourselves" expresses **concern that the nation's past and heritage are inadequately treated** by its own people, rather than foreign forces.
- The overall tone of this comment is **somber and disappointed**, with a clear perspective that contemporary changes represent **a step backward** in both cultural and artistic expression.

INSIGHTS

Mostly relevant, exhaustive, and well-grounded statements

The analogy with the Soviet past likely makes a point about **authoritarian destruction** of art and heritage, and **freedom of expression**, not about patriotism

Using ChatGPT to produce speculative Facebook text on the removal of Cvirka's statue

B. COMPOSITION

PROMPT: COMPOSITION

Compose another comment on the removal of Cvirka's statue based on the delfi.lt news story.

A very important and awaited day in the history of Vilnius city – finally, the monument to Petras Cvirka will be removed. This is not only the removal of a physical symbol of the Soviet era but also a moral victory reflecting our efforts to evaluate history responsibly. Undoubtedly, it has been a long and complex process, considering that our history is intricate and often painfully contradictory. Nevertheless, we must acknowledge that the significance of monuments goes far beyond mere aesthetics or artistic expression – they involve issues of memory and identity. This is an important step in the right direction, albeit one that sparks discussions about historical memory and heritage.

Original text composed in Lithuanian: *Labai svarbi ir laukiama diena Vilniaus miesto istorijoje – pagaliau bus pašalintas Petras Cvirka paminklas. Tai ne tik fizinis sovietinės eros simbolio pašalinimas, bet ir moralinė pergalė, atspindinti mūsų pastangas vertinti istoriją atsakingai. Neabejotinai, tai buvo ilgas ir sudėtingas procesas, atsižvelgiant į tai, kad mūsų istorija yra komplikuota ir dažnai skaudžiai prieštaringa. Vis dėlto, turime pripažinti, kad paminklų reikšmė yra daug daugiau nei tik estetika ar meninė išraiška – tai atminties ir identiteto klausimai. Tai svarbus žingsnis teisinga linkme, nors ir kelia diskusijas apie istorinį atminimą ir paveldą.*

INSIGHTS

The comment reads much like TLDR; text or a summary of the delfi.lt article

Adopts the position of the delfi.lt article

Tone is educated and polished

Deliberative and rational argument

Discourse strategies quite unlike in actual conversation

No metaphors, no pragmatic tropes!

Attribution

Predication

PROMPT: COMPOSITION

Compose another comment on the removal of Cvirka's statue following this comment:

Earlier, everything was destroyed by the Russians, and now by ourselves. Well, what kind of pipe will we build, we are too poor to understand true art.

Original text:
Anksčiau viską griovė rusai, o dabar patys. Na kokį vamzdį pastatys, mes per prasti, kad tikrą meną suprasti.

What kind of days are these today, when our history and culture are being erased right before our eyes? The monument to Cvirka was more than just a bronze figure – it was a testimony to the mistakes and victories of our past, a symbol of our identity. Now, all that remains is cold, impersonal 'modern' creations that lack soul, that lack history. Each demolished monument, each buried page of history, seems like a step back from who we are and where we came from. Culture should be celebrated, not removed, art should inspire, not make our hearts cold. Where has the respect and love gone for what makes us true Lithuanians?

Original text composed in Lithuanian: *Kas per dienos tai šiandien, kai mūsų istorija ir kultūra trinama tiesiai prieš mūsų akis? Cvirkos paminklas buvo daugiau nei tik bronzos figūra – jis buvo liudijimas mūsų praeities klaidoms ir pergalems, mūsų tapatybės simbolis. Dabar viskas, kas lieka, tai šalti, beasmeniai "modernūs" kūriniai, kurie neturi sielos, neturi istorijos. Kiekvienas nugriautas paminklas, užkastas istorijos puslapis, atrodo kaip žingsnis atgal nuo to, kas mes esame ir iš kur atėjome. Kultūra turėtų būti švenčiama, o ne šalinama, menas – turėtų įkvėpti, o ne priversti mūsų širdis šalti. Kur dingio pagarba ir meilė tai, kas mus daro tikrais lietuviais?*

INSIGHTS

Comment rich in **discourse** and **pragmatics**, not unlike some actual comments

Rhetorical questions:

What kind of days are these today...?

Where has the respect and love gone...?

Attribution

Predication

COMPARISON: COMMENTS AGAINST REMOVAL

ChatGPT-generated comment

- our history and culture are being erased right before our eyes
- more than just a bronze figure – a testimony to the mistakes and victories of our past, a symbol of our identity
- cold, impersonal 'modern' creations that lack soul
- each demolished monument, each buried page of history, seems like a step back from who we are and where we came from
- culture should be celebrated, not removed
- art should inspire, not make our hearts cold
- where has the respect and love gone for what makes us true Lithuanians?

Comments in actual FB thread

- the “history of Lithuania is being destroyed”
- the statue “does not bother anyone”
- it belongs to “our history, good or bad”
- “what a pity [that] we try to erase our past”
- politics should stay out of memorialisation, and Cvirka should be assessed only as poet
- “[t]he destroyers of Lithuanian history will erect some iron four-legged cone [and] will call it art to make our children and grandchildren degenerates”
- will be replaced by “another Vilnius pipe” or “loads of scrap metal [like] on the Green Bridge”

Source: Laužikas & Dallas (forthcoming)

Assessing the relevance of this investigation for
the study and reality of populism on social media

POPULISM, SOCIAL MEDIA & CHATGPT

PROMPT 1: ANALYSIS (LT)

Asking for ChatGPT's **definition of populism** (the definition will be used to understand **why ChatGPT identifies specific expressions as populist**).

The response includes **some common, but not all relevant properties** related to populism;

The connection between **populism and criticizing Soviet influence is puzzling, especially as nostalgia for an idealized past** is normally considered a trait of populism.

Populism is a style of political activity and rhetoric that claims to represent **the interests of "ordinary people" as opposed to the elite**. Populist discourse often features **sharp opposition between "ordinary" people and a "corrupt" elite**, while also typically **emphasizing national identity and criticizing Soviet influence**. Populist leaders frequently use a **straightforward, direct speaking style** and portray themselves as defenders of the interests of ordinary people.

Populism can emerge on **both the right and left** sides of the political spectrum, depending on how the concept of "the people" is defined and who is considered the opponent of the elite. Right-wing populism is often associated with **anti-immigrant policies and ethnonationalism**, while left-wing populism usually focuses on **social inequality and criticism of capitalism**.

While some populists may seek positive changes, critics argue that populism can be dangerous to democracy as it encourages autocracy and authoritarianism, undermining the significance of institutions that limit the powers of the government.

PROMPT 2: ANALYSIS (LT)

What are the characteristics that may be used to identify a populist comment?

Criteria identified do not include occurrence of schemas such as **nostalgia** for an idealized past, **conspiracies**, **threats from out-groups or villains**, or narratives of **heroism**, **suffering**, and **betrayal**

- Clearly expresses **hostility towards the "elite" or ruling class.**
- Emphasizes that **current decisions do not reflect the will of the "common people."**
- Utilizes a **simple and emotional style** of language to create a strong emotional connection with the reader.
- May propose **simple solutions to complex problems**, often disregarding facts or real consequences.

PROMPT 3: ANALYSIS (LT)

Review the thread on the removal of Cvirka's statue and identify populist comments, now in English.

ChatGPT identified relevant excerpts with

banal anti-elitist

statements, **sarcasm** and **hyperbole**, and appealing to **emotions**.

No excerpt supporting the removal was selected

It's puzzling why ***The government destroying the past has no future*** and ***History, whatever it may be, needs to be known, not destroyed*** were also identified as populist.

Destroyers of Lithuanian history will build **some iron four-legged contraption** in place of the writer and call it art, **making our children and grandchildren into ignoramus** who don't understand what art and culture are. (L3)

The government destroying the past has no future. (L13) ?

Well, the authorities are **afraid even of dead monumental people**. (L53)

Probably in that place, they will build Dulkys **with a vaccine in their hands**. (L63)

I am just curious if other countries are ashamed of their past. Do they also destroy monuments and **build meaningless structures that do not reflect our current culture?** (L114)

History, whatever it may be, needs to be known, not destroyed. (L35) ?

Original comments in Lithuanian „Lietuvos istorijos naikintojai pastatys vietoj rašytojo kokią nors geležinę keturkoję kerėplą ir pavadins tai menu kad mūsų vaikus ir anūkus padaryt degradais nesuvokiančiais kas yra menas ir kultūra.“ (L3) „Valdžia griauanti praeitį neturi ateities“ (L13) „Nu jo valdžia bijo ir negyvu paminkliniu žmoniu“ (L53) „Turbut toj vietoj Dulki su vakcina rankoj pastatys“ (L63) „Man tik įdomu ar kitos šalys ir gėdijasi savo praeities. Ar ten ir verčia paminklus ir stato niekaverčius statinius kurie neatspindi mūsų dabartinės kultūros“ (L114) „Istorija kokia ji butu reikia žinoti o ne griauti“ (L35)

PROMPT 1: ANALYSIS (EN)

Asking for ChatGPT's **definition of populism in English**, to benefit from the much larger English LLM corpus

The response includes **some common, but not all relevant properties** related to populism;

The connection between **populism and criticizing Soviet influence is puzzling**, especially as **nostalgia for an idealized past** is normally considered a trait of populism.

1. **Appeal to "The People" vs. "The Elite"**: Populism often involves rhetoric that champions **"the people" (seen as virtuous and authentic) against "the elite" (portrayed as corrupt and out of touch)**. This dichotomy is central to populist messaging and can be applied to various contexts, from politics to culture.
2. **Anti-Establishment Sentiment**: Populism typically positions itself as opposed to the established order. This anti-establishment stance is not limited to politics but can also encompass opposition to intellectual, cultural, or economic elites.
3. **Simplification of Complex Issues**: Populist discourse often simplifies complex issues into **easily digestible narratives**. This simplification is a way to appeal to a broad audience and make issues more relatable.
4. **Emotional Appeal**: Populism frequently relies on emotional appeal rather than detailed policy discussions. This can include stirring up feelings of **nostalgia for the past**, fear of change, or anger against perceived injustices.
5. **Crisis, Breakdown, or Threat Narrative**: Populists often frame situations as crises or **existential threats to the way of life, culture, or nation**. This sense of urgency can justify radical changes or the bypassing of established norms and processes.
6. **Moralistic Language**: Populism uses moralistic language to frame political and social discourse. It often presents issues **in terms of right and wrong, moral and immoral**, rather than as complex policy debates.
7. **Direct Relationship with "The People"**: Populists often claim to have a direct connection with the people, bypassing traditional institutional channels. This connection can be established through charismatic leadership, social media, or public rallies.

PROMPT 2: ANALYSIS (EN)

To get **more context on how ChatGPT worked**:

On the basis of **your knowledge about the phenomenon of populism**, do you see any examples of **populist discourses, ideas and ways of communication** in the comments? Could you **identify and quote exactly such comments**, and **provide a commentary** for each of them?

Destroyers of Lithuanian history will replace the writer with some iron four-legged freak and call it art, to make our children and grandchildren degenerates, not understanding what art and culture are. This comment strongly criticizes cultural changes, framing them as destructive to national heritage and future generations. It uses **dramatic and emotional language** to appeal to **a sense of cultural preservation**, a common aspect of populist rhetoric that emphasizes traditional values and resistance to change.

Era of idiots' rampage. This succinct comment is a direct attack on the current state of affairs, suggesting a decline in quality and sensibility in decision-making. This kind of **blunt, unfiltered criticism** is typical of populist discourse, aiming to **resonate with people's frustrations and anger** towards the **perceived incompetence of the elite** or authorities.

They are already starting to destroy history. This comment **accuses the authorities of erasing history**, a common theme in populist discourse. It implies a **betrayal** of the nation's legacy and an attack on collective memory, seeking to **mobilize sentiment** against perceived cultural and **historical injustice**.

Original comments:

Lietuvos istorijos naikintojai pastatys vietoj rašytojo kokią nors geležinę keturkoję kerėplą ir pavadins tai menu, kad mūsų vaikus ir anūkus padaryt degradais, nesuvokiančiais, kas yra menas ir kultūra.

Idiotų siautėjimo era.

Jau pradeda naikinti istorija.

PROMPT: COMPOSITION (EN)

Based on the actual thread, produce a speculative Facebook conversation between users with different profiles and characteristics, responding to the delfi.lt post.

Surprisingly, **less confrontational or populist!**

Justinas Mikalauskas (Supportive of Removal): "Finally, a step in the right direction. Cvirka's ties to the Soviet regime can't be ignored."

Ieva Kazlauskaitė (Against Removal, Responding to Justinas): "@Justinas Mikalauskas, It's not just about his political ties. Cvirka is a part of our literary history. Removing the statue doesn't change history."

Martynas Pocius (Reflective): "I understand both sides, but shouldn't we focus on educating people about our complex history instead of removing statues?"

Dalia Vilkas (Conservative, Responding to Martynas): "@Martynas Pocius, Exactly! Erasing symbols doesn't erase the past. We need to remember and learn, not hide."

Rokas Jankūnas (Sarcastic, Cynical): "Watch them replace it with some modern art that nobody understands. Symbolism over substance, as usual."

Greta Balčiūnaitė (Progressive, Responding to Rokas): "@Rokas Jankūnas, It's not about the replacement. It's about not glorifying a controversial figure. Art evolves, just like society."

Lukas Navickas (Questioning): "What's next then? Are we going to reevaluate every historical figure? Where does it end?"

Aistė Juškevičienė (Educational, Responding to Lukas): "@Lukas Navickas, It's about context and understanding. Not every historical figure is the same. We need to discuss and educate, not oversimplify."

Vytautas Gedminas (Provocative): "So we're just going to sanitize our history to make it more 'palatable'? That's not how you respect the past."

Simona Petrauskienė (Hopeful, Concluding): "Maybe this space can be a place for something new that represents our growth as a nation. Something that unites us."

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CONCLUDING THOUGHTS

THANK YOU!

Costis Dallas, Rimvydas Laužikas

**Connective Research Group
Faculty of Communication
Vilnius University**

Contact: konstantinos.dallas@kf.vu.lt

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